

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF 1 : 1 COMPLEXES OF Ce^{III} $\mu = 1.00 M KCl$

Ligands	log K at temp. (°C)			ΔH k cal mol ⁻¹ at temp. (difference of 10°)		ΔG k cal mol ⁻¹ at temp. (°C)			ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ at temp. (°C)		
	25	35	45	(35-25)	(45-35)	25	35	45	25	33	45
	L-Alanine	6.10	5.60	5.00	-21.14	40.28	-8.37	-7.94	-7.32	-42.83	-42.85
L-Glutamine	3.72	3.15	2.65	-24.09	-37.95	-5.11	-4.47	-3.88	-63.70	-63.71	-107.14
L-Asparagine	3.52	3.60	-2.60	-21.99	-39.097	-4.83	-4.25	-3.80	-57.58	-57.60	-110.99

chloric acid were used to maintain pH of the test solution at 2.70 ± 0.02 .

pH measurements were made on a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter. Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording polarograph (C. I. C., India). The capillary used had an 'm' value 2.18 mg s^{-1} and drop time 3.0 s at 43.0 cm effective height of mercury. Nitrogen gas was passed to remove dissolved oxygen from the solution before recording the polarograms. Measurements were made at 25, 35 and 45°.

Results and Discussion

A well defined three electron reversible reduction wave of Ce^{III} has been reported^{12,13} at pH 2.70 ± 0.02 in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelatin used as a maximum suppressor. The slopes of linear plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs $E_{a,e}$ were of the order of $21 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ for Ce^{III} and its complexes with all the three ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The straight line plots of j_a vs $\sqrt{h}$ for metal ion and its complexes showed the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves. The reduction potential of Ce^{III} was -1.85 V against S.C.E. at pH 2.70 ± 0.02 .

The half-wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. The method of Lingane¹⁴ was used to determine composition and stability constants. Thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the well known thermodynamic relations¹⁵ and tabulated in Table 1.

The order of stability constants of Ce^{III} complexes with respect to ligands was found L-asparagine < L-glutamine < L-alanine and decrease with the increase of temperature.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Head of the Department of Chemistry, for facilities.

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Physicochemical Studies of Complex Formation of Cyclopentane Tetracarboxylic Acid with Alkaline Earth Metals

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Manuscript received 20 May 1985, revised 16 September 1985,
accepted 17 January 1986

CIS, cis, cis, cis-1,2,3,4-Cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid (CPTA) and its different compounds were used for various purposes, such as in resins and rubber preparation¹, for plasticisers², and for surface treatment of metals and plasters³. So far, a systematic study of its complexes seems to be lacking although as a quadridentate ligand it has been of great interest in coordination chemistry. The present investigation deals with the determination of the formation constants of the all *cis*-

cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid complexes of alkaline earth metals in aqueous medium using the Irving-Rossotti titration technique. The nature of the metal-ligand bond (in solids) of the complexes has been explained by studying their ir spectra and correlated with the formation constants of the complexes.

Experimental

A 0.05 M solution of the ligand, CPTA (Matheson; m.p. 195-96°) was prepared in double distilled water. Stock solutions of metals were prepared from their metal nitrates, and standardised gravimetrically⁵. Stock solutions were diluted to 0.01M solutions for pH-metric titrations.

pH values were measured using a pH meter (pH 821, Electronic Corporation of India) with an expanded scale having an accuracy of ± 0.02 log units and sensitivity ± 0.01 . The temperature was always maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following sets of solutions (total volume = 50 ml, ionic strength (μ) = 0.19 M HClO₄) were titrated against carbonate-free NaOH (0.2 M): (i) 10 ml 0.05 M HClO₄ + 9 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 31 ml H₂O, (ii) 10 ml 0.05 M HClO₄ + 10 ml 0.05 M ligand + 9 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 21 ml H₂O, and (iii) 10 ml 0.05 M HClO₄ + 10 ml 0.05 M ligand + 9 ml 1 M NaClO₄ + 5 ml 0.01 M metal salt solution + 16 ml H₂O. The metal to ligand ratio was kept 1 : 10 in all the titrations to satisfy the highest coordination number of the respective metal ion.

Equal volumes of equimolar solutions of the metal nitrates and ligand were mixed to isolate the complexes. The pH of the solutions were raised from 6.5 to 7.5 and the clear solutions were concentrated. On addition of ethanol the solid complexes were obtained which were filtered, washed several times with water-ethanol mixture and dried at 60-70°.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants were calculated considering four dissociable carboxylic groups in CPTA. The values of $\bar{n}H/(1-\bar{n}H)$ were plotted in the regions $0 < \bar{n}H < 1$, $1 < \bar{n}H < 2$, $2 < \bar{n}H < 3$, $3 < \bar{n}H < 4$. Such plots were linear (Fig. 1) and all the points falling on the linear curves in the above regions were considered for the calculation of $\log pK_1^H$, $\log pK_2^H$, $\log pK_3^H$ and $\log pK_4^H$, the values of which come out to be 9.1709, 4.9500, 3.9313 and 2.5101, respectively. Metal-ligand stability constants of the complexes were calculated by applying least-square technique to the $\bar{n}$, pL data. The formation curves were drawn by plotting $\bar{n}$ vs pL values (Fig. 2) From these formation curves, the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for different metal complexes are given in Table 1.

The stability constants of alkaline earth metal complexes follow the order, $Be^{2+} > Mg^{2+} < Ca^{2+} > Sr^{2+} > Ba^{2+}$ (Table 1). Be^{2+} forms strongest complex

in the series, while Mg^{2+} has lower stability constant value than Ca^{2+} as observed in case of other similar ligands^{6,7}.

Fig. 1. Proton-ligand stability constant *cis, cis, cis, cis*-cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid. Plot of $\log \frac{\bar{n}H}{1-\bar{n}H}$ vs pH: (A) $3 < \bar{n}H < 4$, (B) $2 < \bar{n}H < 3$, (C) $1 < \bar{n}H < 2$, and (D) $0 < \bar{n}H < 1$.

Fig. 2. Formation of CPTA complexes with metal(II): (O) Be, (x) Mg, (●) Ca, (---) Sr and (Δ) Ba.

The nature of metal-ligand bond can be determined by studying the infrared spectra⁸⁻¹⁰. Table 2 reveals frequencies of COO⁻ groups due to antisym-

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF ALKALINE EARTH METAL-CPTA COMPLEXES

 $\mu = 0.19 M$, temp = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Metal(II)	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Be	6.46 (± 0.03)	4.90 (± 0.05)
Mg	6.00 (± 0.05)	—
Ca	6.15 (± 0.04)	2.90 (± 0.06)
Sr	5.90 (± 0.05)	2.85 (± 0.04)
Ba	5.38 (± 0.07)	2.84 (± 0.04)

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION PEAKS OF CARBOXYLIC GROUPS (ANTISYM. AND SYM.) AND THEIR DIFFERENCES IN ALKALINE EARTH METAL COMPLEXES

Metal(II)	ν_{COO^-} (antisym.) cm^{-1}	ν_{COO^-} (sym.) cm^{-1}	Frequency difference cm^{-1}
Be	1 600	1 379	221
Mg	1 550	1 360	190
Ca	1 540	1 388	152
Sr	1 540	1 418	122
Ba	1 526	1 408	118

mmetrical and symmetrical vibrations and their differences in CPTA-alkaline earth metal complexes. It can be seen that the differences of the frequencies in the region 1 660 to 1 525 and 1 420 to 1 360 cm^{-1} show the decrease in the order, $Be^{2+} > Mg^{2+} > Ca^{2+} > Sr^{2+} > Ba^{2+}$ which is also the order of their ionic radii. This suggests that the order of decreasing stabilities of the complexes should also be same¹¹. This is true for stability values except there is reversal in case of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} complexes because Mg^{2+} forms hydrate bonds in aqueous medium.

The study indicates that Be—O bond is less ionic in character than other alkaline earth metal complexes and this trend increases with the increase in their ionic radii.

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Effect of Nitro Group on the Mass Spectra of Quinazolinone Derivatives[†]

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Manuscript received 21 May 1979, accepted 11 September 1985

BEHAVIOUR of 4(3H-quinazolinone derivatives under electron impact have been studied earlier¹⁻³ but no attempt, however, appears to have been made to study the effect of nitro group on the phenyl part of the quinazolinone ring. In the absence of appropriate deuterated compounds, an attempt has been made to study the gross change in the breakdown pattern under electron impact ionisation conditions in the mass spectral study of this class of compounds possessing substituents on the phenyl part of the quinazolinone ring. The results obtained with the EI-MS-computer system are presented in this communication.

(6) R = CH₃, R₁ = morpholino

Earlier studies of various quinazolinone derivatives studied under electron impact mass spectrometry invariably led to the fragmentation of the pyrimidine part of the quinazolinone ring. Substituents such as nitro group with or without *ortho*-amino function should, in principle, exhibit their well known behaviour under electron impact⁴. Studies carried out with 1-6 revealed that the heterocyclic ring in 1 was not cleaved initially. The percentage abundance of the peaks appearing due to the loss of O, NO, NO₂ and also due to the loss of CO, CH₃CN and (CO + HCN) fragments, suggest that the predominant pathway of the breakdown appears to be mediated through the NO₂ group. In compounds 2-5, the absence of peaks

C.D.R.I. Communication No. 2543.